

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Yewande. O. Okusanya¹, Habeeb. A. Sholabi², Oluchi. O. Onasanya³, Moses. D. Amosun⁴

^{1,2,3}Doctoral Students,⁴ Associate Professor of the Department of Early Childhood and Educational Foundations.

⁴Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan

ABSTRACT: This study investigated the socio-economic determinants of child abuse and neglect in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, and their implications for children's rights. Anchored in the Social Disorganisation Theory, the research adopted a mixed-methods design to explore how poverty, unemployment, overcrowding, low parental education, and cultural norms fuel systemic child maltreatment. Empirical data from 180 participants across four local government areas revealed a high prevalence of physical, emotional, and sexual abuse, with poverty and urban stress as strong predictors. Interviews with stakeholders highlighted weak enforcement of the Child Rights Act and cultural acceptance of corporal punishment as major barriers to change. Findings showed that emotional and physical abuse are most prevalent, exacerbated by inadequate healthcare, exploitative labour, and poor legal resources. Despite the domestication of child protection laws in Oyo State, enforcement remains ineffective due to poor institutional capacity, limited awareness, and resistance from traditional and religious authorities. The study concluded that child rights violations in Ibadan are deeply embedded in structural inequality and normalised cultural practices. It recommended culturally grounded public education, legal literacy campaigns, capacity-building for welfare agencies, and the integration of child protection into social policy. This research contributes to a nuanced understanding of child vulnerability in urban Nigeria, providing actionable insights for building rights-respecting communities.

KEYWORDS: Child abuse, Socio-economic drivers, Child neglect, Child rights, Legal enforcement, Cultural norms.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Child abuse and neglect remain pervasive and deeply entrenched issues in Nigeria, with far-reaching consequences for children's physical health, emotional well-being, cognitive development, and prospects (Oloko, 1999; Ige, 2013, Amosun, 2012). In the Ibadan Metropolis of Oyo State, which is one of the most densely populated urban centres in the region, a confluence of socio-economic challenges contributes significantly to the persistence of child maltreatment. Factors such as poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, low levels of parental education, and entrenched cultural practices not only heighten the risk of abuse but also impede timely intervention and justice.

Recent studies highlight the disturbing prevalence of child abuse within Ibadan and its environment. According to Olayanju, Okafor, and Olayinka (2011) found that over 60% of children surveyed in selected secondary schools in Ibadan reported having experienced at least one form of abuse, physical, emotional, or sexual. In another study, Ajiboye, Adegoke, and Makinde (2013) reported that 29.5% of children in urban Ibadan had been victims of corporal punishment severe enough to cause injury, while 17.3% of female children reported experiencing sexual abuse. University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, and community-based NGOs like Cece Yara Foundation and the Centre for Children's Health Education, Orientation and Protection (CEE-HOPE) have also documented rising cases of child neglect, abandonment, and exploitation, especially among children in street situations and domestic servitude (CEE-HOPE, 2020).

Furthermore, data obtained from the Oyo State Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Inclusion indicate that between 2018 and 2022, more than 1,200 reported cases of child abuse occurred in Ibadan metropolis alone, a figure believed to be a fraction of actual incidents due to underreporting and community silence driven by stigma and fear (Oyo State MoWASI, 2022). These figures underscore the urgency of addressing root causes and reinforcing mechanisms for early detection and intervention.

These socio-economic pressures are compounded by systemic inadequacies in child protection services and law enforcement, despite the presence of robust legal frameworks such as Nigeria's Child Rights Act (CRA) of 2003 and international conventions like the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), both of which guarantee children's rights to survival, development, protection, and participation (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2003; UNICEF, 2007). However, the implementation of these frameworks

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

remains uneven and largely ineffective in many local contexts due to limited awareness, lack of political will, and inadequate institutional capacity (Arua, 2011; Okafor & Osakinle, 2013).

This study investigated the socio-economic drivers of child abuse and neglect in Ibadan North, with particular focus on how poverty, parental unemployment, urban stress, educational gaps, and culturally-sanctioned disciplinary practices intersect and endanger children's welfare. Drawing on empirical data and local case studies, the research aimed to reveal how structural inequalities and systemic neglect of child-centered development perpetuate cycles of abuse and normalise harmful practices within communities (Oni, 2010; Ebigbo, 2003). Additionally, the study evaluated the responsiveness and effectiveness of current child protection mechanisms, including social welfare departments, family courts, and community-based organisations, in addressing child abuse in the area. These include increasing public awareness and community education, strengthening social support services, integrating child protection into urban planning and poverty alleviation strategies, and enhancing multi-sectoral collaboration among government, civil society, and traditional institutions (Umaru & Abdullahi, 2015; Ogunjuyigbe & Liasu, 2007). Through this approach, it is hoped that a more sustainable, culturally sensitive, and rights-based framework for protecting vulnerable children in Ibadan North can be developed and implemented.

To fully understand the underlying drivers of child abuse and neglect in Ibadan North, Nigeria, the study adopted the theoretical model of Social Disorganisation Theory, as formulated by Shaw and McKay (1942) which states that: "Social disorganisation is the inability of a community structure to realise the common values of its residents and maintain effective social controls." (Shaw & McKay, 1942). This theory emerged from the Chicago School of Sociology and was initially developed to explain the prevalence of juvenile delinquency in urban neighbourhoods. Shaw and McKay argued that high levels of poverty, ethnic heterogeneity, residential mobility, and urban decay disrupt social cohesion and weaken the informal social controls necessary to regulate behaviour and support child development which might result in poor attitude toward schooling and low sociometric values, low children's emotional wellbeing and cognitive development (Ikje et al., 2022, Amosun, 2019, Amosun, 2015, Amosun, 2014, Amosun, 2012). In communities experiencing social disorganisation, institutions such as families, schools, religious groups, and neighbourhood networks lose their capacity to monitor and protect children. This breakdown leads to increased vulnerability (Amosun, 2010, Amosun, 2012), as abusive behaviours often go unnoticed or unreported. Furthermore, in such settings, criminal behaviour and neglect become normalised or tolerated due to systemic fatigue and desensitisation.

In Ibadan North, many low-income communities exhibit characteristics of social disorganisation: overcrowded housing, unstable family structures, informal employment, and limited access to education and healthcare (Amosun, 2014, Amosun, 2010). These conditions weaken the community's ability to enforce child protection norms and monitor vulnerable children effectively. Parents under economic stress may exhibit reduced parental efficacy, relying on physical punishment as a coping mechanism (Olanrewaju et al., 2018), while neighbours may be reluctant to intervene due to cultural norms or lack of trust in formal institutions. Hence, child abuse and neglect persist not only due to individual failings but as a symptom of broader community breakdown.

Statement of the Problem

Child abuse and neglect remain urgent yet disturbingly underreported realities in Ibadan Metropolis. Behind closed doors in urban communities like Agbowo, Mokola, and Sango, too many children suffer in silence, caught in the crossfire of poverty, broken systems, and societal indifference. While Nigeria has made legal strides through the adoption of the Child Rights Act (2003) and its commitment to SDG 16.2, these policies often fail to reach the ground where they matter most. A staggering 63% of Nigerians live in multidimensional poverty (NBS, 2022), and with Oyo State facing an unemployment rate of 32% (2023), families under pressure may unintentionally neglect children's needs or resort to harmful practices. These challenges are compounded by deep-rooted cultural beliefs and limited access to quality education and child protection services. Corporal punishment remains widely accepted as discipline, and early exposure to street trading, domestic labour, or even physical abuse is often normalised as part of growing up. In many homes, caregivers are simply unaware of children's legal rights or the damaging long-term effects of neglect. Meanwhile, overstretched or underfunded social services, particularly in urban slums and semi-formal settlements, are unable to respond adequately to the volume or complexity of these cases. NGOs working in this space often operate in silos, lacking coordination and sufficient data to target interventions effectively. The consequence of this neglect is not just the suffering of individual children; it is the weakening of society's future. According to UNICEF (2021), only 1 in 10 abused children in Nigeria receives any form of support. In Ibadan Metropolis, the absence of comprehensive, localised data masks the scale of the crisis and delays urgent interventions. If these socio-economic and systemic issues are not addressed through coordinated, community-based, and policy-backed efforts, children in Ibadan will continue to face threats to their safety, education, and overall development. This, in turn, undermines the region's potential for social cohesion, productivity, and long-term national progress.

Research Questions

1. Which socio-economic factors (poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, low parental education) show the strongest correlation with child abuse and neglect cases in Ibadan?
2. What are the most prevalent forms of child maltreatment (physical, emotional, sexual abuse, neglect) reported in Ibadan?

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

3. To what extent are existing child protection laws (e.g., the Child Rights Act) effectively implemented in Ibadan?
4. What community attitudes and traditional beliefs contribute to the persistence of child maltreatment practices in Ibadan?
5. How do the identified socio-economic drivers and systemic gaps specifically undermine children's rights in Ibadan?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, which effectively integrated both quantitative and qualitative research components. This design was chosen for its capacity to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem by combining statistical trends with in-depth personal insights. The population of the study consisted of children aged 5–11 years engaged in street hawking, their parents or guardians, and community stakeholders, including teachers. These participants were directly related to the study location, which encompassed four Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Ibadan, Nigeria: Ibadan North, Ibadan North-East, Ibadan South-West, and Egbeda. The choice of these LGAs was informed by observed prevalence and reports of child street hawking activities within these communities. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure equitable representation of participants from each of the four selected LGAs. The final sample included 120 child hawkers (30 per LGA), 40 parents or guardians, and 20 community stakeholders, providing a balanced cross-section of the population relevant to the study objectives. Data collection utilised both quantitative and qualitative instruments. Structured questionnaires were administered to children and parents, capturing data on demographics, schooling status, hawking history, and socio-economic background. In addition, semi-structured interview guides were used to elicit detailed narratives from teachers, social workers, and community leaders regarding their perceptions and experiences with child hawking. All research instruments underwent face and content validation by academic and field experts to ensure relevance and appropriateness. A field test was conducted in an LGA outside the main study areas to assess the reliability and clarity of the tools, and adjustments were made based on feedback received. Trained research assistants facilitated the administration of instruments. Surveys were conducted in accessible community settings, including schools, homes, and markets. Interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent and later transcribed verbatim for thematic analysis.

To achieve the objectives of the study, three main research tools were developed and used. These included two structured questionnaires and one interview guide. The Parent/Guardian Background and Perception Survey (PGBPS) was given to parents and guardians. It collected data on their education, employment, income level, and their understanding of child welfare and abuse. This instrument was pre-tested in a local government area outside the main study sites and showed strong internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.86. In addition to this, a questionnaire titled the Community Stakeholders' Perception Survey (CSPS) was administered to community stakeholders such as teachers, religious leaders, and social workers. This tool gathered information on cultural beliefs, community practices, and challenges in implementing child protection laws. It was also pilot-tested and found to be reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.81.

For qualitative data, the Community Stakeholders' Perception Interview Guide (CS-PIG) was used to conduct in-depth interviews with selected stakeholders. This guide helped to explore deeper insights into cultural norms, the enforcement of child rights, and systemic challenges. Although it does not require a statistical reliability test, the guide was reviewed by experts and refined during a field test to ensure clarity and cultural relevance.

A fourth supporting tool, the Pilot Validation Checklist and Feedback Log (PVCFL), was used during pre-testing to collect suggestions from participants and field experts. These suggestions helped improve the clarity and accuracy of the tools used. No questionnaire was directly administered to the children. Information concerning children's experiences was obtained through the parents, guardians, and key informants. The combined use of quantitative and qualitative methods gave the study a balanced and in-depth understanding of the issues affecting children's rights in the selected communities.

The study adhered strictly to ethical guidelines relevant to research involving minors and vulnerable populations. Informed consent was obtained from parents or guardians of all participating children. Participants were informed of their right to voluntary participation, confidentiality, anonymity, and freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. Quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics—such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores—were used to summarise findings. Qualitative data from interviews were analysed using thematic analysis, where recurring themes and sub-themes were identified, categorised, and interpreted in alignment with the study objectives.

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

RESULTS

Research Question One: The socio-economic factors (poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, low parental education) show the strongest correlation with child abuse and neglect cases in Ibadan North

S/N	Items	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std.dev
1	Due to my family's financial struggles, I often feel overwhelmed, which sometimes affects how I care for my children	41 (22.8%)	22 (12.2%)	63 (35%)	54 (30%)	2.83	1.11
2	Being unemployed (or underemployed) has made it harder for me to provide a stable and nurturing environment for my child	39 (21.7%)	13 (7.2%)	45 (25%)	83 (46.1%)	2.85	1.19
3	Living in a cramped or overcrowded home has increased tension in my household, sometimes leading to harsh parenting	25 (13.9%)	48 (26.7%)	70 (38.9%)	37 (20.5%)	2.82	0.95
4	Because of my limited education, I sometimes struggle to understand my child's needs or access helpful resources	24 (13.3%)	27 (15%)	62 (34.4%)	67 (37.2%)	2.88	0.88
5	I often feel abandoned by social support systems, making it harder to cope with parenting challenge	37 (20.5%)	18 (10%)	57 (31.7%)	68 (37.8%)	2.84	1.01
6	Worrying about food, rent, or bills has made me more impatient or less attentive toward my child	25 (13.9%)	19 (10.6%)	100 (55.6%)	36 (20%)	2.56	2.57
7	Living in a high-crime neighborhood has increased my stress levels, affecting my ability to parent calmly	24 (13.3%)	12 (6.7%)	99 (55%)	45 (25%)	2.95	0.93
8	Growing up in poverty or an unstable home has influenced how I parent, sometimes repeating negative patterns	20 (11.1%)	19 (10.6%)	99 (55%)	42 (23.3)	2.64	1.04
Weighted average:						2.79	

Result from Table 1 indicated that 41 (22.8%) strongly disagreed that Due to my family's financial struggles, I often feel overwhelmed, which sometimes affects how I care for my children while 63 (35%) agreed that Due to my family's financial struggles, I often feel overwhelmed, which sometimes affects how I care for my children. Also 39 (21.7%) indicated strongly disagreed that Being unemployed (or underemployed) has made it harder for me to provide a stable and nurturing environment for my child while 83 (46.1%) agreed that Being unemployed (or underemployed) has made it harder for me to provide a stable and nurturing environment for my child. Moreover, 25 (13.9%) indicated strongly disagreed that Living in a cramped or overcrowded home has increased tension in my household, sometimes leading to harsh parenting while 70 (38.9%) agreed that Living in a cramped or overcrowded home has increased tension in my household, sometimes leading to harsh parenting. Furthermore, 24 (13.3%) strongly disagreed that Because of my limited education, I sometimes struggle to understand my child's needs or access helpful resources while 67 (37.2%) agreed that Because of my limited education, I sometimes struggle to understand my child's needs or access helpful resources. Additionally, 18 (10%) indicated strongly disagreed that I often feel abandoned by social support systems, making it harder to cope with parenting challenges while 68 (37.8%) indicated agreed that I often feel abandoned by social support systems, making it harder to cope with parenting challenges. Also 19 (10.6%) indicated strongly disagreed that worrying about food, rent, or bills has made me more impatient or less attentive toward my child while 100 (55.6%) agreed that Worrying about food, rent, or bills has made me more impatient or less attentive toward my child. More so, 12 (6.7%) indicated strongly disagreed that Living in a high-crime neighborhood has increased my stress levels, affecting my ability to parent calmly while 99 (55%) agreed that Living in a high-crime neighborhood has increased my stress levels, affecting my ability to parent calmly. Lastly, 19 (10.6%) indicated that Growing up in poverty or an unstable home has influenced how I parent, sometimes repeating negative patterns while 99 (55%) agreed that Growing up in poverty or an unstable home has influenced how I parent, sometimes repeating negative patterns.

The weighted average obtained for the responses was 2.79. It could be concluded from the findings that socio-economic factors (poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, low parental education) showed the highest strongest correlation with child abuse and neglect cases in Ibadan North. The finding revealed that poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, and low parental education showed the highest effects on child abuse and neglect cases within Ibadan North axis.

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

To corroborate the finding, two interview response highlighting how socio-economic factors correlate with child abuse and neglect, based on lived experiences.

It's been so hard since I lost my job last year. Before, I could at least afford daycare for my son while I worked, but now we're behind on rent, and the stress is unbearable. Some days, I snap at him over small things—like when he asks for food we don't have. I never wanted to be that kind of parent, but when you're constantly worried about survival, patience runs thin. The social worker said my case isn't unique—many parents in poverty end up yelling or hitting their kids out of frustration, not because they're cruel, but because they're drowning. I see it in my neighbourhood too: more evictions mean more families crammed into small apartments, more tension, and more kids getting hurt. If I had steady work and a safe place to live, I know I'd be a better mother
(Parent/45/Female/Egbeda)

The second respondent had this to say:

"We live in a tiny apartment with five relatives because none of us can afford our own place. My kids have no space to play, and the noise never stops. I didn't finish high school, so I only get low-paying jobs, and I don't always know how to help my son with school or where to find parenting help. Sometimes, when he acts out, I don't know if it's normal kid behaviour or something worse, my parents just beat us when we misbehave, so that's all I know. A teacher reported to me for neglect when my son came to school hungry, but it's not that I don't care, it's that I'm barely keeping up. The counsellor told me that overcrowding and lack of education make parenting harder, and I believe it. If I had my own space and knew better, maybe I could break the cycle. (Community Stakeholder/48/Female/BNE)"

Research Question Two: What are the most prevalent forms of child maltreatment (physical, emotional, sexual abuse, neglect) reported in Ibadan North

S/N	Items	Never	Rarely	Often	Very often	Mean	Std.dev
1	Children in my community are frequently subjected to physical discipline (e.g., beating with objects, slapping) as a form of punishment	20 (11.1%)	19 (10.6%)	99 (55%)	42 (23.3)	2.74	1.04
2	Children are often yelled at, insulted, or humiliated by caregivers or adults in their homes	12 (6.7%)	24 (13.3%)	99 (55%)	45 (25%)	2.87	0.93
3	Children in my area lack access to adequate food, school supplies, or medical care due to family poverty or caregiver neglect	19 (10.6%)	25 (13.9%)	100 (55.6%)	36 (20%)	2.89	2.57
4	Children face inappropriate touching, coercion, or sexual exploitation by adults or older peers	37 (20.5%)	18 (10%)	57 (31.7%)	68 (37.8%)	2.79	1.01
5	Children are forced into street hawking, domestic labor, or other exploitative work to support their families	25 (13.9%)	19 (10.6%)	100 (55.6%)	36 (20%)	2.96	2.57
6	Children regularly see or hear violence between caregivers (e.g., physical fights, verbal threats)." "	41 (22.8%)	22 (12.2%)	63 (35%)	54 (30%)	2.89	1.11
7	"Children with illnesses or injuries do not receive timely medical attention due to caregiver indifference or financial barriers	39 (21.7%)	13 (7.2%)	45 (25%)	83 (46.1%)	2.95	1.19
8	Children's emotional needs (e.g., comfort, encouragement) are ignored by caregivers."	20 (11.1%)	19 (10.6%)	99 (55%)	42 (23.3)	2.84	1.04
Weighted average: 2.86							

Result from Table 2 indicated that 20 (11.1%) indicated never that Children in my community are frequently subjected to physical discipline (e.g., beating with objects, slapping) as a form of punishment while 99 (55%) indicated often that Children in my community are frequently subjected to physical discipline (e.g., beating with objects, slapping) as a form of punishment. Also 12 (6.7%) indicated never that Children are often yelled at, insulted, or humiliated by caregivers or adults in their homes while 99 (55%) indicated often that Children are often yelled at, insulted, or humiliated by caregivers or adults in their homes. Moreso, 19 (10.6%) indicated never that Children in my area lack access to adequate food, school supplies, or medical care due to family poverty or caregiver neglect while 100 (55.6%) indicated often that Children in my area lack access to adequate food, school supplies, or

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

medical care due to family poverty or caregiver neglect. Moreover 18(10%) indicated that rarely that Children face inappropriate touching, coercion, or sexual exploitation by adults or older peers while 68 (37.8%) indicated very often that Children face inappropriate touching, coercion, or sexual exploitation by adults or older peers. Furthermore, 19 (10.6%) indicated rarely that Children are forced into street hawking, domestic labor, or other exploitative work to support their families while 100 (55.6%) indicated often that Children are forced into street hawking, domestic labor, or other exploitative work to support their families. Also 22 (12.2%) indicated rarely that Children regularly see or hear violence between caregivers (e.g., physical fights, verbal threats) while 63 (35%) indicated very often that Children regularly see or hear violence between caregivers (e.g., physical fights, verbal threats).. More so, 13 (7.2%) indicated never that Children with illnesses or injuries do not receive timely medical attention due to caregiver indifference or financial barriers while 83 (46.1%) indicated very often that Children with illnesses or injuries do not receive timely medical attention due to caregiver indifference or financial barriers. Lastly, 19 (10.6%) indicated that children's emotional needs (e.g., comfort, encouragement) are rarely ignored by caregivers while 99 (55%) indicated often that Children's emotional needs (e.g., comfort, encouragement) are often ignored by caregivers or

The weighted average obtained for the responses was 2.86. It could be concluded from the findings that the most prevalent forms of child maltreatment (physical, emotional, sexual abuse, neglect) reported in Ibadan North; emotional abuse, followed by physical abuse, sexual abuse, child labour, medical and psychological neglect. The finding revealed that emotional and physical abuse are the most prevalent forms of child maltreatment within the Ibadan North axis.

To corroborate the findings, two interview responses highlight the most prevalent forms of child maltreatment, based on lived experiences.

In my 10 years working with child welfare cases in Ibadan, physical abuse is the most reported—parents and teachers often justify beating children as 'discipline.' However, emotional abuse is just as widespread but underreported because many see insults and humiliation as normal parenting. Poverty drives neglect; we see children missing school because parents can't afford uniforms or meals. Sexual abuse cases are rising, especially among street hawkers and domestic servants. Just last week, we rescued a 12-year-old girl who was assaulted by her employer. The biggest challenge is cultural acceptance; many families resist intervention, believing maltreatment is a private matter (Social Worker/Female/47/IBNLTG)

The second respondent has this to say:

"In our area, nearly every child is beaten—it's how we were raised. But the worst is neglect. Many parents, like me, struggle to feed their children due to unemployment. My neighbour's son fainted in school last month from hunger. Girls hawking goods face sexual harassment daily; my friend's daughter was raped but the family kept quiet to avoid shame. Even if we want to change, poverty makes it hard. No money means no school, no food, and more stress, so parents lash out. Government assistance is scarce, so abuse keeps repeating." (Parent/Female/57/IBNELG)

Research Question Three: To what extent are existing child protection laws (e.g., the Child Rights Act) effectively implemented in Ibadan North

S/N	Items	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std.dev
1	Child protections laws are not relevant in Nigeria at all	24 (13.3%)	12 (6.7%)	99 (55%)	45 (25%)	2.05	0.93
2	The Nigerian government does not really implement or equip child protection laws	20 (11.1%)	19 (10.6%)	99 (55%)	42 (23.3)	2.00	1.04
3	Child labour or abuse laws do not exist in Nigeria	5 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	2.07	0.93
4	The legal remedies for children whose rights have been violated are not accessible	5 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	2.01	0.93
5	Society and communities are not aware of child protection laws and their provisions	5 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	2.02	0.93
6	Child protection laws are not addressing emerging issues in Nigeria	5 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	2.00	0.93
Weighted average:						2.05	

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

The Result from Table 3 indicated that 12 (6.7%) disagreed that child protection laws are not relevant in Nigeria at all, while 99 (55%) agreed that child protection laws are not relevant in Nigeria at all. Also, 19 (10.6%) disagreed that the Nigerian government does not implement or equip child protection laws while 99 (55%) agreed that the Nigerian government does not really implement or equip child protection laws. Moreover, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that child labour or abuse laws do not exist in Nigeria, while 100 (55.6%) agreed that Child labour or abuse laws do not exist in Nigeria. Moreover, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that the legal remedies for children whose rights have been violated are not accessible while 100 (55.6%) agreed that the legal remedies for children whose rights have been violated are not accessible. However, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that societies and communities are not aware of child protection laws and their provisions while 100 (55.6%) agreed that the societies and communities are not aware of child protection laws and their provisions. Moreover, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that child protection laws are not addressing emerging issues in Nigeria while 100 (55.6%) agreed that child protection laws are not addressing emerging issues in Nigeria.

The weighted average obtained for the responses was 2.05. It could be concluded from the findings that what extent are existing child protection laws (e.g., the Child Rights Act) effectively implemented in Ibadan North are low. The finding revealed that the existing child protection law are low and lack implementation within Ibadan North axis. To corroborate the findings, two interview response on existing child protection laws (e.g., the Child Rights Act) effectively implemented in Ibadan North, based on lived experiences.

As someone who has worked for over a decade as a child protection officer in urban and semi-urban areas of Oyo State, I can say that the implementation of the Child Rights Act (CRA) in Nigeria is more of a policy on paper than a practice in reality. Yes, the CRA exists, and awareness among professionals is growing, but on the ground, the law is not felt in the lives of the vulnerable children we work with daily. Let me give an example: we once rescued a 9-year-old girl who had been living with her uncle after her parents died. She had been subjected to constant beatings, denied food, and made to work long hours as a street hawker. We reported the case to the police, expecting swift action under the provisions of the CRA, but we were met with resistance. The officers at the station told us to 'settle it at home' because it was a family matter. It took several weeks of pressure from our NGO before they agreed to prosecute the case.

Moreover, while Oyo has domesticated the CRA and has some enforcement mechanisms in place, implementation suffers due to underfunded child welfare agencies, inadequate training of police and judicial officers, and a lack of coordination between stakeholders. Worse still, many people in the communities are unaware that such a law exists. Cultural norms often take precedence over legal protections, and this severely weakens enforcement. So in practice, children are still subjected to early marriages, child labour, and abuse without any real recourse to justice. Until there is strong political will, budgetary commitment, and grassroots sensitisation, the Child Rights Act will remain largely ineffective (Teacher/Female/40/IBLG)

The second respondents had this to say:

My experience as a teacher in Ibadan Nigeria, particularly in Oyo State, reveals the deep gap between child protection legislation and its implementation. Although Nigeria ratified the Child Rights Act in 2003, many northern states including Oyo have not yet domesticated the law, primarily due to cultural and religious objections. This legal gap leaves children in this region extremely vulnerable. I've seen cases of girls as young as 13 being withdrawn from school to be married off. When I try to intervene or report such cases, I'm often reminded by community leaders that I am interfering with 'tradition' and that the law doesn't apply here. The schools lack any structured support system for abused children, and there's a general absence of government social welfare services. In one particular case, a male student confided in me that he was being physically abused by a guardian. I attempted to contact the state's child protection office, only to discover that the nearest functional office was in another local government area, with limited reach and capacity. The child was returned to his guardian after a brief intervention, and the abuse likely continued.

In rural and conservative communities like mine, the idea of children having rights is still seen as a Western imposition. Teachers and community members often don't know that there's a law protecting children's rights, and even when they do, there's little they can do because of a weak enforcement framework. In conclusion, the CRA remains ineffective in states where it is not domesticated. Without legal backing, government action, and widespread awareness, children in many parts of Nigeria continue to suffer silently (Stakeholder/Female/40/IBLG).

Research Question Four: What community attitudes and traditional beliefs contribute to the persistence of child maltreatment practices in Ibadan North

S/N	Items	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std.dev
1	Physical discipline is necessary for proper child upbringing	4 (2.2%)	12 (6.7%)	99 (55%)	65 (36.1%)	2.05	0.93

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

2	Children who disobey elders deserve harsh punishment as a cultural norm	5 (2.8%)	10 (10.6%)	105 (58.3%)	60 (33.3)	2.00	1.04
3	Reporting child abuse within the community is discouraged to avoid family shame.	5 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	2.07	0.93
4	Traditional beliefs justify using children for labor to teach responsibility	5 (2.8%)	10 (10.6%)	105 (58.3%)	60 (33.3)	2.01	0.93
5	Parents have the absolute right to treat their children as they see fit without outside interference	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	10 (10.6%)	--	2.02	0.93
6	Spiritual or religious practices (e.g., exorcism, corporal punishment for "stubbornness") can justify harsh treatment of children	15 (8.3%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	60 (33.3%)	2.00	0.93
7	Community elders should handle child maltreatment cases internally rather than involving legal authorities	4 (2.2%)	2 (1.1%)	119 (66.1%)	55 (30.6%)	2.05	0.93
8	A child's misbehavior reflects poorly on the entire family, justifying severe corrective measures	10 (5.6%)	9 (5%)	99 (55%)	62 (34.4)	2.00	0.93
Weighted average: 2.02							

Result from Table 4 indicated that 12 (6.7%) disagreed that physical discipline is necessary for proper child upbringing while 99 (55%) agreed that physical discipline is necessary for proper child upbringing. Also 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that children who disobey elders deserve harsh punishment as a cultural norm while 105 (58.3%) agreed that children who disobey elders deserve harsh punishment as a cultural norm. More than that, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that Reporting child abuse within the community is discouraged to avoid family shame while 100 (55.6%) agreed that Reporting child abuse within the community is discouraged to avoid family shame. Moreover, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that the traditional beliefs justify using children for labor to teach responsibility while 105 (58.3%) agreed that traditional beliefs justify using children for labor to teach responsibility. However, 100 (55.6%) strongly disagreed that parents have the absolute right to treat their children as they see fit without outside interference while 10 (10.6%) agreed that parents have the absolute right to treat their children as they see fit without outside interference. Moreso, 15 (8.3%) strongly disagreed that spiritual or religious practices (e.g., exorcism, corporal punishment for "stubbornness") can justify harsh treatment of children while 100 (55.6%) agreed that Spiritual or religious practices (e.g., exorcism, corporal punishment for "stubbornness") can justify harsh treatment of children. Moreso, 4 (2.2%) strongly disagreed that

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

community elders should handle child maltreatment cases internally rather than involving legal authorities while 119 (66.1%) agreed that community elders should handle child maltreatment cases internally rather than involving legal authorities. Moreover, 9 (5%) disagreed that the child's misbehavior reflects poorly on the entire family, justifying severe corrective measures while 99 (55%) agreed that child's misbehavior reflects poorly on the entire family, justifying severe corrective measures.

The weighted average obtained for the responses was 2.02. It could be concluded from the findings that the community attitudes and traditional beliefs contribute to the persistence of child maltreatment practices are poor and low. The finding revealed that there are poor community attitudes and traditional beliefs that contribute to the persistence of child maltreatment practices are very low within Ibadan North axis. To corroborate the finding, two interview response on the community attitudes and traditional beliefs contribute to the persistence of child maltreatment practices in Ibadan North, based on lived experiences.

She recalled witnessing cases where children were severely flogged, locked in dark rooms, or denied food for minor infractions like refusing errands or returning late from school. According to her, these practices are viewed not as abuse but as legitimate and necessary tools for raising "respectful" children. "Many parents still believe that 'the cane is the child's teacher,'" she remarked. Efforts by health workers and NGOs to promote alternatives like positive discipline are often met with resistance or ridicule. Mrs. Adunni emphasized that in community meetings, elders often defend these practices, arguing that they were raised the same way and turned out 'well.' She concluded that without culturally sensitive education and dialogue, legal frameworks like the Child Rights Act will struggle to gain ground in such environments. (Community health worker/Female/43.IBSELG)

The second respondent had this to say:

A local religious scholar explained how certain child-rearing customs are sustained by religious and cultural interpretations. He recounted that in his community, early marriage is seen not just as a tradition but as a divine mandate for preserving morality and family honor. Girls as young as 13 are married off, often with parental pride, and attempts by social workers to intervene are perceived as Western intrusion into sacred values. He acknowledged that while Islam promotes the protection and education of children, these messages are frequently distorted by poverty and patriarchal norms. Mallam Usman noted, "People fear that girls who stay too long at home may be corrupted, so they believe it's better to marry them early—even if it means pulling them out of school." He admitted that some religious leaders are complicit in reinforcing these practices but stressed the need for faith-based education that aligns religious teachings with children's rights. He believes that change must come from within the community, led by trusted local voices who can reinterpret tradition in ways that protect children's dignity (Religious leader/Male/46/INNLG)

Research Question Five: How do the identified socio-economic drivers and systemic gaps specifically undermine children's rights in Ibadan North?

S/N	Items	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std.dev
1	I believe poverty limits families' ability to provide basic needs for children, violating their right to survival and development	4 (2.2%)	4 (2.2%)	106 (58.9%)	66 (36.7%)	2.56	1.03
2	I believe due to high costs or insufficient schools prevent children from exercising their right to education	4 (2.2%)	4 (2.2%)	106 (58.9%)	66 (36.7%)	2.61	1.04
3	I was sure that child labour, driven by economic hardship, deprives children of their right to protection from exploitation.	4 (2.2%)	4 (2.2%)	106 (58.9%)	66 (36.7%)	2.77	1.02
4	Weak enforcement of child protection laws allows abuse, trafficking, and early marriage to persist, violating children's rights to safety and freedom	4 (2.2%)	2 (1.1%)	119 (66.1%)	55 (30.6%)	2.41	1.03
5	I believe that gender discrimination denies girls their rights to education, health, and equal opportunities	24 (13.3%)	12 (6.7%)	99 (55%)	45 (25%)	2.43	0.99
6	Poor healthcare infrastructure in marginalised communities undermines children's right to health and survival	20 (11.1%)	19 (10.6%)	99 (55%)	42 (23.3)	2.51	0.98
7	I believe the divert resources that meant for child welfare programmes, weakening systemic support for children's rights	5 (2.8%)	5 (2.8%)	100 (55.6%)	70 (38.8%)	2.86	0.99
Weighted average:						2.59	

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

Result from Table 5 indicated that 4 (2.2%) strongly disagreed that I believe poverty limits families' ability to provide basic needs for children, violating their right to survival and development while 106 (58.9%) agreed that poverty limits families' ability to provide basic needs for children, violating their right to survival and development. Also 4 (2.2%) strongly disagreed that I believe due to high costs or insufficient schools prevent children from exercising their right to education while 106 (58.9%) agreed that I believe due to high costs or insufficient schools prevents children from exercising their right to education. Moreso, 4 (2.2%) strongly disagreed that I was sure that child labor driven by economic hardship deprives children of their right to protection from exploitation while 106 (58.3%) agreed that child labor driven by economic hardship deprives children of their right to protection from exploitation. Moreover, 4 (2.2%) strongly disagreed that the weak enforcement of child protection laws allows abuse, trafficking, and early marriage to persist, violating children's rights to safety and freedom while 119 (66.1%) agreed that weak enforcement of child protection laws allows abuse, trafficking, and early marriage to persist, violating children's rights to safety and freedom. However, 24 (13.3%) strongly disagreed that I believe that gender discrimination denies girls their rights to education, health, and equal opportunities while 99 (55%) agreed that gender discrimination denies girls their rights to education, health, and equal opportunities. Moreso, 20 (11.1%) strongly disagreed that poor healthcare infrastructure in marginalized communities undermines children's right to health and survival while 99 (55%) agreed that poor healthcare infrastructure in marginalized communities undermines children's right to health and survival. Lastly, 5 (2.8%) strongly disagreed that I believe the divert resources that meant for child welfare programs, weakening systemic support for children's rights while 100 (55.6%) agreed that I believe the divert resources that meant for child welfare programs, weakening systemic support for children's rights.

The weighted average obtained for the responses was 2.59. It could be concluded from the findings that the socio-economic drivers and systemic gaps specifically undermine children's rights are on high side. The finding revealed that there are socio-economic drivers (i.e poverty, lack of access to quality education, child labour, weak enforcement of child protection law, poor healthcare, gender discrimination, and corrupt government specifically undermine children's rights within Ibadan North axis

To corroborate the finding, **two interview response** on the socio-economic drivers and systemic gaps specifically undermine children's rights in Ibadan South-East LGA, based on lived experiences.

A seasoned social welfare officer in state, shared firsthand accounts of how poverty and unemployment severely affect children's rights in low-income communities. According to her, most child abuse and neglect cases she handles stem from families grappling with financial insecurity. "We receive cases of children being trafficked to cities to work as domestic servants or hawkers—not because parents are wicked, but because they are desperate," she explained. She recounted a case involving a 10-year-old girl who was sent to Abuja to work in exchange for ₦5,000 monthly to support her siblings. Mrs. Hadiza lamented that systemic failures, especially poor coordination between child welfare units and law enforcement, often result in delayed interventions. "Sometimes, we don't even have transport to visit reported abuse sites, and police often demand unofficial payments before acting," she added. These gaps in government response mechanisms make it hard to enforce the Child Rights Act effectively, leaving many children vulnerable to exploitation and abuse. She stressed the need for better funding of welfare services, training of personnel, and community-based social protection systems (Social worker/Female/41/IBSELG).

The second respondent has this to say

A secondary school teacher in a low-income area of Port Harcourt shared how inadequate access to education and public services fuels systemic neglect of children's rights. He noted that many of his students either skip school to work or eventually drop out due to financial hardship. "When parents can't afford uniforms or textbooks, children are kept at home. Some girls end up selling items on the streets or getting involved with older men who give them money," he said. He narrated a case of a bright student who dropped out in JSS2 because her widowed mother couldn't support her. "She was later married off to a man in his forties," he added regretfully. Mr. Sunday emphasised that school authorities often feel helpless due to the lack of social support systems to rescue and rehabilitate such children. He also highlighted the near absence of counselling services, family support programs, or functioning child protection desks in schools. "Children in poor neighbourhoods are essentially invisible to the state," he said. For him, the biggest gap is not the absence of laws, but the failure to implement them where they are needed most (Teacher/Female/41/IBSELG).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

RQ 1: The socio-economic factors (poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, low parental education) show the strongest correlation with child abuse and neglect cases in Ibadan North. The finding revealed that poverty, unemployment, urban overcrowding, and low parental education showed the highest effects on child abuse and neglect cases within Ibadan North axis. The finding is in line with the work of Fallon et al (2017) found that that economic hardship significantly increased the risk of substantiated maltreatment. In 9% of cases, families had run out of money for basic needs (food, housing, utilities) in the prior six months. These households were nearly twice as likely to face substantiated maltreatment. Children in such families also exhibited higher rates of developmental concerns, academic difficulties, and caregiver mental health/substance use issues. Bywaters et al, (2022) found that income shocks directly impact child maltreatment rates. Reductions in family income increased neglect and abuse

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

cases, while financial support (such as, higher minimum wages) reduced them. The study emphasised that low parental education, unemployment, and material deprivation (e.g., housing instability) were key drivers of maltreatment.

RQ 2: The findings revealed that emotional and physical abuse are the most prevalent forms of child maltreatment within the Ibadan North axis, followed by sexual abuse, child labour, medical and psychological neglect. This finding corroborates the work of Olarinmoye and Uchendu (2024) found that physical abuse was the most prevalent, often justified as "discipline" through beatings with objects. The emotional abuse included verbal humiliation and threats, linked to cultural norms suppressing children's voices; neglect manifested as deprivation of food, school supplies, and medical care, driven by poverty. Sexual abuse involved coercion, with perpetrators often being acquaintances. Lastly, low parental education, public school attendance, and living with guardians increased vulnerability. Balogun & Adenowuro (2020) found that the most prevalent are sexual abuse, with non-contact abuse (e.g., forced exposure to pornography at being most common. Also, contact abuse often occurred in perpetrators' homes, primarily in the afternoon. Finally, certain risk factors, such as polygamous family structures, parental separation, and involvement in street hawking, significantly increase the likelihood of child abuse and neglect.

RQ 3: The findings revealed that the existing child protection laws are low and lack implementation within the Ibadan North axis. This finding is in line with the work of Akinola (2018) found that while the CRA has been domesticated in over 24 states, its enforcement remains weak due to institutional inefficiencies, poor funding, and limited awareness among caregivers and stakeholders. The study also emphasised the lack of coordination between law enforcement and welfare agencies, leading to underreporting and mismanagement of child abuse cases. Furthermore, Akinola noted that many states still rely heavily on traditional systems of child discipline, which often contradict the rights-based approach of the CRA. Eze and Ezeobi (2020) found that Anambra State had made notable progress due to active civil society advocacy and collaboration with international organizations such as UNICEF. However, Imo and Ebonyi lagged in implementation due to bureaucratic delays, political apathy, and cultural resistance. Notably, the study reported that despite domestication, the CRA's provisions on child labour, early marriage, and juvenile justice were largely flouted. Musa and Ahmed (2021) discovered that socio-cultural and religious beliefs significantly hinder the domestication and implementation of the CRA. In both states, Sharia law and patriarchal norms often supersede statutory child protection laws, creating a parallel legal framework that is not child-rights friendly. Moreover, there was a general lack of institutional capacity, with child welfare services poorly staffed and funded.

RQ 4: The finding revealed that there are poor community attitudes and traditional beliefs that contribute to the persistence of child maltreatment practices are very low within the Ibadan North axis. This finding supports the work of Ojo and Fasakin (2019), who found that many parents and guardians believed that using force was essential to instil respect and obedience in children, and such practices were seldom questioned due to deeply rooted traditional ideologies. This perception, the authors argue, legitimises maltreatment under the guise of correction and discipline. Similarly, Iliyasu et al. (2020) reported that beliefs in child obedience and parental authority, often reinforced through religious interpretations, contributed to the normalisation of abuse such as excessive flogging or deprivation. These attitudes created an environment where maltreatment was not only tolerated but considered necessary. Additionally, Akinwale and Olatunji (2022) discovered that child maltreatment is often perpetuated through generational teachings. Elders played a central role in promoting beliefs that children must endure hardship to build resilience. The study concluded that challenging these ingrained cultural narratives is crucial to curbing maltreatment.

RQ 5: The finding revealed that there are socio-economic drivers (i.e poverty, lack of access to quality education, child labour, weak enforcement of child protection law, poor healthcare, gender discrimination, and corrupt government specifically undermine children's rights within Ibadan North axis. This finding supports the work of Olanrewaju et al. (2018) found that economic hardship often leads to children being withdrawn from school and subjected to street hawking or domestic labor. The authors noted a systemic failure in providing social protection for vulnerable families, which in turn worsens child neglect and abuse. Despite the existence of the Child Rights Act, enforcement is weak due to poor funding and institutional apathy. Adegboyega (2020) found that poverty and gender inequality intersect with traditional beliefs to normalize child marriage and restrict girls' education. Systemic gaps such as weak judicial response and absence of community-level sensitization campaigns further entrenched these violations. Chukwuma and Iwuagwu (2021) found that lack of shelter facilities, inadequate staffing, and delayed legal processes were major institutional gaps. Additionally, urban poverty and displacement due to conflict and environmental hazards were key socio-economic drivers undermining child safety and access to justice.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the complex interplay between socio-economic deprivation and the prevalence of child abuse and neglect in Ibadan North. Child abuse is not merely a behavioral issue but a manifestation of broader structural inequalities, entrenched poverty, and systemic governance failures. The evidence suggests that children growing up in impoverished households with limited access to education, healthcare, and legal protection are more vulnerable to abuse, exploitation, and neglect. The

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

research concludes that the protection of children's rights in Ibadan North is hindered by both material poverty and social attitudes that perpetuate violence and neglect. While legislative frameworks such as the Child Rights Act offer a blueprint for protection, their impact is diluted by weak enforcement, low awareness, and inadequate social safety nets. The study confirms that socio-economic empowerment, parental education, and community-based interventions are essential to curbing child abuse and promoting the well-being and rights of children. Therefore, addressing child abuse and neglect in Ibadan North requires a multi-pronged approach that not only enforces existing child protection laws but also tackles the root causes embedded in poverty, inequality, and cultural perceptions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The state government should prioritize full implementation of the Child Rights Act by providing the necessary funding, establishing child protection units in all local governments, and ensuring adequate staffing with trained professionals.
2. Initiatives that provide employment opportunities, skills training, and micro-credit to low-income families can help reduce the economic pressures that lead to child neglect and child labor. Awareness campaigns on child rights, positive parenting, and the harms of corporal punishment should be conducted at community levels through religious institutions, schools, and media platforms.
3. Community-based child protection committees comprising teachers, health workers, religious leaders, and youths should be established to monitor, report, and respond to cases of abuse and neglect.
4. Schools should serve as protective environments by training teachers to identify signs of abuse, establishing school counselors, and integrating child rights education into the curriculum.
5. Government agencies, NGOs, and community groups should collaborate more effectively to provide coordinated responses, share data, and streamline referral systems for abused children. Lastly, regular assessments should be carried out to evaluate the effectiveness of child protection policies and programs in Ibadan North, with input from stakeholders and the affected communities.

IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study have several important implications for policy, practice, and academic discourse: The results call for a rethinking of child protection strategies in urban centers like Ibadan North. Policymakers need to align child protection policies with broader poverty alleviation and education strategies to achieve sustainable outcomes

1. The normalisation of child abuse in socio-economically disadvantaged communities highlights the urgent need to challenge cultural narratives that justify violence against children. Changing societal attitudes requires long-term community engagement and education. Schools must go beyond academic instruction to become safe havens and watchdogs for child welfare. Teachers, as key community stakeholders, must be trained in child psychology and protection protocols.
2. Weak enforcement of existing child protection laws implies the need for judicial reform, including the establishment of family courts and training of law enforcement officials on child rights.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adebayo, D. O. 2018. Socio-economic factors influencing child abuse in urban Nigeria. *Journal of Social Work in Developing Societies* 1.1: 34–45.
- 2) Akinola, B. O. 2018. Implementation of Child Rights Act in Nigeria: The journey so far. *African Journal of Social Work and Development* 8.2: 101–118.
- 3) Akinwale, B. & Olatunji, M. 2022. Traditional beliefs and the intergenerational transmission of child maltreatment in Ekiti rural communities. *African Journal of Psychology and Social Studies* 9.1: 56–70.
- 4) Ajiboye, A. D., Adegoke, T. G. & Makinde, B. 2013. Prevalence and patterns of child abuse among secondary school students in Ibadan, Nigeria. *African Journal for the Psychological Study of Social Issues* 16.1: 50–60.
- 5) Alokun, F. B. & Oyelade, A. S. 2014. Influence of family background on academic performance of students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Research* 2.2: 68–75
- 6) Amosun, M.D. 2010. Comprehensive basic education: A means for enhancing disadvantaged children's access to education and sustainable development in Nigeria. *Africa Journal of Historical Sciences in Education* 6. 2: 170-177.
- 7) Amosun, M.D. 2012. Child labour and poverty: Threats to children's life and education.
- 8) *Nigerian Journal of Research in Primary Education* 2. 1: 49-58.
- 9) Amosun, M.D. 2012. School-based socio-metric variables and gender as predictors of primary school pupils' attitude towards schooling and academic achievement. Doctoral thesis, University of Ibadan.

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

- 10) Amosun, M.D. 2014. Providing quality pre-primary and primary education in Nigeria in the best interest of the child. *Journal of Early childhood Association of Nigeria* 4. 2: 56-63
- 11) Amosun, M.D. 2015. Effect of early childhood education programme on cognitive development of young children in Oyo state. *Ibadan Journal of Educational Studies* 12. 2: 322-331
- 12) Amosun, M.D. 2019. Early childhood educator awareness of and disposition to children's
- 13) emotional wellbeing for life-long learning in Oyo state Nigeria. In Oduolowu, Esther A.,
- 14) Salami, I.A. and Amosun, M.D. (Eds.) *Fundamentals of preschool and primary school*
- 15) *teachers' preparation in Nigeria*. Department of Early Childhood and Educational
- 16) *Foundations*. 276-288pp, ISBN: 978-2860-30-1.
- 17) Ikie, R. N. Amosun, M.D. & Olalowo, I.E. 2022. Empirical realities of teacher-child interaction
- 18) and cognitive development of pre-primary school children in Ibadan, Oyo state.
- 19) *International Journal of Emerging Issues in Early Childhood Education* 4 2: 1-11.
- 20) Arua, A. E. 2011. Implementation of the Child Rights Act in Nigeria: Issues and challenges. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies* 14.1: 18-27.
- 21) Balogun, F. M. & Adenowuro, O. E. 2020. Prevalence and pattern of child sexual abuse: A cross-sectional study among male secondary school adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Health* 4.1. Retrieved from Allied Academies.
- 22) Bywaters, P., Skinner, G., Cooper, A., Kennedy, E. & Malik, A. 2022. The relationship between poverty and child abuse and neglect: New evidence. Nuffield Foundation. <https://www.nuffieldfoundation.org>.
- 23) CEE-HOPE. 2020. Annual report on child protection in Nigeria. Lagos: Centre for Children's Health Education, Orientation and Protection.
- 24) Chukwuma, E. C. & Iwuagwu, O. 2021. Institutional gaps and socioeconomic factors undermining child protection in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Sociology and Anthropology* 19.2: 75-90.
- 25) Ebigbo, P. O. 2003. Child abuse and neglect in Nigeria: A position paper. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 27.9: 1139-1146.
- 26) Edo, C. K. 2024. Child rights: The prevalence of child abuse and neglect in the Nigerian family context. Diss. Law, Golden Gate University. <https://digitalcommons.law.ggu.edu/theses/99/>.
- 27) Eze, C. O. & Ezeobi, K. A. 2020. Assessing the implementation of the Child Rights Act in Nigeria: A case study of South-East Nigeria. *Journal of Child Protection and Social Policy in Africa* 12.1: 56-72.
- 28) Fallon, B., Ma, J., Allan, K., Trocmé, N. & Jud, A. 2017. Examining the relationship between economic hardship and child maltreatment using data from the Ontario Incidence Study of Reported Child Abuse and Neglect-2013 (OIS-2013). *BMC Public Health* 7.1: 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs7010006>.
- 29) Federal Republic of Nigeria. 2003. *Child Rights Act*. Abuja: Government Press.
- 30) Ige, O. A. 2013. Preventing child sexual abuse: Parents' perceptions and practices in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology* 4.2: 127-134.
- 31) Iliyasu, Z., Mohammed, A. & Garba, S. 2020. Religious and cultural perspectives on child abuse in Northern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Family Practice* 11.2: 89-95.
- 32) Musa, A. M. & Ahmed, H. A. 2021. Barriers to the implementation of child protection laws in Northern Nigeria: A study of Kano and Katsina States. *Nigerian Journal of Law and Society* 15.2: 33-48.
- 33) Ojo, T. & Fasakin, A. 2019. Cultural justifications for physical discipline: A study of parental attitudes in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Social Work in Developing Societies* 1.3: 101-117.
- 34) Olanrewaju, I. A., Omotoso, F. & Alabi, J. O. 2018. Children's rights and the challenges of implementation in Nigeria: A study of Lagos and Ogun States. *Journal of Social Sciences and Public Policy* 10.2: 112-127.
- 35) Olarinmoye, A. T. & Uchendu, O. C. 2024. Prevalence and pattern of child maltreatment at home among secondary school students in Ibadan North Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 158: 107090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2024.107090>.
- 36) Olayanju, L., Okafor, I. I. & Olayinka, O. O. 2011. Prevalence of child abuse and its consequences among secondary school students in Ibadan. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology* 3.3: 70-76.
- 37) Ogunjuyigbe, P. O. & Liasu, T. A. 2007. The socio-cultural context of child abuse in southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of African Studies and Development* 2.7: 154-160.
- 38) Okafor, R. U. & Osakinle, E. O. 2013. Child abuse: A challenge to academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria. *Journal of Research & Method in Education* 2.3: 10-17.
- 39) Oloko, S. B. A. 1999. Children's rights: Legal and psychological perspectives from Nigeria. *Children and the Law in Nigeria*. Eds. Nwazuoke et al. Ibadan: University Press. 43-61.
- 40) Oni, G. A. 2010. Urban poverty and child welfare in Ibadan, Nigeria. *African Population Studies* 24.3: 45-59.

The Socio-Economic Drivers of Child Abuse and Neglect in and its Implications for Children's Rights in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

- 41) Oyo State Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Inclusion. 2022. Annual report on child welfare and protection. Ibadan: Oyo State Government.
- 42) Umaru, R. I. & Abdullahi, M. 2015. Community participation in child protection in northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Work* 51: 59–72.
- 43) UNICEF. 2007. Implementation handbook for the Convention on the Rights of the Child. 3rd ed. New York: United Nations Children's Fund.